

Article

Droplet digital PCR is a novel screening method identifying potential cardiac G-protein coupled receptors as candidate pharmacological targets in a rat model of pressure-overload-induced cardiac dysfunction

Nabil V. Sayour^{1,2,3#}, Viktória É. Tóth^{1,2,3#}, Regina N. Nagy¹, Imre Vörös^{1,2,3}, Tamás G. Gergely^{1,2,3}, Zsófia Onódi^{1,2,3}, Noémi Nagy⁴, Csaba Bödör⁴, Barnabás Váradi^{1,2}, Mihály Ruppert⁵, Tamás Radovits⁵, Federico Bleckwedel^{6,7}, Laura C. Zelarayán^{6,7}, Pal Pacher⁸, Bence Ágg^{1,9,10}, Anikó Görbe^{1,10}, Péter Ferdinady^{1,9,10}, Zoltán V. Varga^{1,2,3*}

¹ Department of Pharmacology and Pharmacotherapy, Semmelweis University, Budapest, Hungary

² HCEMM-SU Cardiometabolic Immunology Research Group, Budapest, Hungary

³ MTA-SE Momentum Cardio-Oncology and Cardioimmunology Research Group, Semmelweis University, Budapest, Hungary

⁴ 1st Department of Pathology and Experimental Cancer Research, Semmelweis University, Budapest, Hungary

⁵ Heart and Vascular Center, Semmelweis University, Budapest, Hungary

⁶ Institute of Pharmacology and Toxicology, University Medical Center Goettingen (UMG), 37075 Göttingen, Germany

⁷ German Center for Cardiovascular Research (DZHK) partner site Goettingen, Germany

⁸ Laboratory of Cardiovascular Physiology and Tissue Injury, National Institute of Health/National Institute on Alcohol Abuse and Alcoholism, Rockville, MD, USA

⁹ MTA-SE System Pharmacology Research Group, Department of Pharmacology and Pharmacotherapy, Semmelweis University, Budapest, Hungary.

¹⁰ Pharmahungary Group, Szeged

* Correspondence: varga.zoltan@med.semmelweis-univ.hu

These authors contributed equally

Abstract: Identification of novel drug targets is needed to improve outcomes of heart failure (HF). G-protein coupled receptors (GPCRs) represent the largest family of targets for already approved drugs providing opportunity for drug-repurposing. Here we aimed (i) to investigate differential expressions of 288 cardiac GPCRs by droplet digital PCR (ddPCR) and bulk RNA sequencing (RNAseq) in a rat model of left ventricular pressure-overload, (ii) to compare RNAseq findings with that of ddPCR, and (iii) to screen and test for novel, translatable GPCR drug targets in HF. Male Wistar rats subjected to transverse aortic constriction (TAC, n=5) showed significant systolic dysfunction vs. sham operated animals (SHAM, n=5) by echocardiography. In TAC vs. SHAM hearts, RNAseq identified 69, and ddPCR identified 27 significantly differentially expressed GPCR mRNAs, 8 of which were identified by both methods showing correlation between the two methods. Of these, Prostaglandin-F2 α -receptor (*Ptgfr*) was further investigated and localized on cardiomyocytes and fibroblasts in murine hearts by RNA-Scope. Antagonising *Ptgfr* by AL-8810 reverted angiotensin-II-induced cardiomyocyte hypertrophy *in vitro*. In conclusion, using ddPCR as a novel screening method we identify GPCR targets in HF. We also show that antagonism of *Ptgfr* could be a novel target in HF by alleviating cardiomyocyte hypertrophy.

Keywords: heart failure; G-protein-coupled receptor; GPCR; prostaglandin F2 α receptor; *Ptgfr*; cysteinyl leukotriene receptor 1; *Cysltr1*; drug repurposing; droplet digital PCR; ddPCR

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Graphical abstract: Through a systematic screening and selection approach, prostaglandin F_{2α} receptor was identified and validated to be a novel and translatable target in heart failure. GPCR: G-protein coupled receptor; RNAseq: mRNA sequencing; ddPCR: droplet digital polymerase chain reaction; Ptgfr: prostaglandin F_{2α} receptor; NRCM: neonatal rat cardiomyocyte; ANG-II: angiotensin-II; CSA: cell surface area.

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1. Introduction

Despite the current advances in the pharmacotherapy for heart failure (HF), this disease remains to be a leading cause of mortality and hospitalization worldwide. Thus, development of new therapeutic approaches is needed [1]–[4].

Studying novel pathomechanisms in HF is of paramount importance for identifying future drug targets, however, developing an entirely new drug from discovery to approval is time- and resource-consuming, and still, is of low success rate, especially in the cardiovascular field [5], [6]. Nevertheless, drug repurposing (a.k.a drug repositioning), i.e. the use of already approved drugs for novel indications, may decrease the risk, cost and time of the drug developmental process, as these drugs have already passed clinical Phases I-II-III, and their safety has already been assessed [7]. For drug repositioning purposes, the family of G-protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs), representing the largest family of targets for already approved drugs, may offer adequate candidates for novel HF indications, since these are importantly involved in the physiology and pathophysiology of cardiovascular diseases [8].

There are GPCRs, such as β -adrenoceptors and angiotensin-II receptor type 1, that are already targeted by drugs approved for HF treatment in the clinical practice (i.e., by β -blockers and angiotensin receptor blockers, respectively) [9]. In addition, several other GPCRs has been shown to play a pivotal role in HF in the preclinical models of HF, and therefore, are of promising translational value [10]. However, no systematic screening with predefined selection criteria for novel cardiac GPCR targets has been achieved so far in HF.

Despite the fact that GPCRs as drug targets are appealing, detecting their expression on a protein level (e.g. by western blot or proteomics) is difficult and largely unsuccessful [11], because (i) GPCRs are insoluble integral membrane proteins that contain seven membrane-spanning helices, (ii) their relative expression is low, (iii) their protein-dynamics and conformational diversity is currently often unresolved, and (iv) there is a lack of specific and high-affinity antibodies. Therefore, transcriptomic analysis of GPCR expression is still a very useful approach to perform and can be used to screen for novel drug targets in the normal and diseased tissues.

For transcriptomic profiling, bulk RNA sequencing is an unbiased, highly sensitive and high-throughput method, and therefore, it became the gold standard choice for target screening on the level of gene expression. Nevertheless, sequence processing requires extensive bioinformatic resources to perform quality control, read mapping and differential gene expression analyses [12]. Droplet digital polymerase chain reaction (ddPCR) on the other hand is a highly precise, absolute quantitative method for analysing gene expression in a unit of measure of copies/ μ L, and does not require bioinformatic background to obtain comparable transcriptomic data [13]. Although ddPCR may not be feasible to analyse the whole transcriptome, when the transcriptional profiling is restricted to a family of targets, e.g. to GPCRs, ddPCR provides unbiased data.

Here we hypothesized that the expression of cardiac GPCRs differs in conditions of cardiac dysfunction compared to physiological states, and that some of these differentially expressed cardiac GPCRs may be targets for already approved drugs. In addition, we hypothesized that beside bulk deep RNA sequencing, ddPCR is also a feasible method for unbiased screening within a family of targets, i.e. GPCRs. To this end, we aimed to investigate the differential expression of GPCR genes of pressure-overload-induced cardiac dysfunction vs. healthy rat hearts by bulk deep RNA sequencing and by ddPCR. Then, we aimed to select cardiac GPCRs for further investigation based on the following criteria: (i) only those GPCRs that were found to be significantly differentially expressed by bulk deep RNA sequencing and by ddPCR, (ii) of these, GPCRs that show significant correlation in expression measured by bulk deep RNA sequencing and by ddPCR, (iii) of these, GPCRs that have never been investigated in the context of cardiac dysfunction before, and have commercially available pharmacological modulators. Finally, we aimed to test the efficacy of this/these drugs in an *in vitro* model of cardiomyocyte hypertrophy.

2. Results

2.1 Echocardiographic characterization of pressure-overload-induced cardiac dysfunction in rats

To identify novel pharmacological targets for HF with a high possibility to be a candidate for drug repurposing, we aimed to investigate GPCR expression in pressure-overload-induced cardiac dysfunction vs. normal rat hearts. To this end, we used a widely established rat model by performing TAC surgery [14] and assessed cardiac function and morphology by terminal echocardiography (Figure 1.). TAC surgery significantly reduced ejection fraction, cardiac output and fractional shortening compared to SHAM surgery at 15-18 weeks following operation. These findings were paralleled by a significant enlargement in cardiac dimensions, i.e., an increase in end-systolic and end-diastolic volumes and a significantly decreased stroke volume in the TAC group compared to the SHAM. Morphological analyses showed a significant increase in anterior, posterior and relative wall thicknesses of the heart, resulting in a significantly higher calculated left ventricular mass in the TAC vs. SHAM group (Figure 1.). All in all, TAC surgery caused a severe phenotype of left ventricular pressure-overload-induced systolic dysfunction and cardiac hypertrophy, as expected [15]. After terminal echocardiography, cardiac samples were obtained from the left ventricles of both TAC vs. SHAM animals, and comparative transcriptional analyses were performed (Figure 2/A.).

Figure 1.

Figure 1.: Echocardiographic parameters 15 weeks after transverse aortic constriction or sham surgery in rats. Left upper panel represents the experimental design. TAC: transverse aortic constriction; LVEF: left ventricular ejection fraction; LVCO: left ventricular cardiac output; LVFS: left ventricular fractional shortening; LVS: left ventricular stroke volume; LVEDV: left ventricular end-diastolic volume; LVESV: left ventricular end-systolic volume; LVAWTd: left ventricular anterior wall thickness in diastole; LVPWTd: left ventricular posterior wall thickness in diastole; RWT: 130

relative wall thickness; **LVMass**: calculated left ventricular mass. Measurements were performed on n=5 individual animals for both the SHAM and the TAC groups. *: p<0.05, unpaired Student's t-test, shown as mean ± SEM.

2.2 Bulk RNA sequencing identified 69, and ddPCR identified 27 cardiac GPCR genes to be differentially expressed in TAC vs. SHAM rat hearts

After the completion of *in vivo* disease modelling, unbiased whole transcriptome analysis on the cardiac samples of both TAC and SHAM hearts was performed by bulk RNA sequencing, resulting in a total of 5864 genes to be significantly differently expressed in TAC vs. SHAM hearts, after correcting for multiple comparisons (*Supplementary table S1* shows all significantly differentially expressed genes found by bulk RNA sequencing). Of note, several genes characteristic to the failing heart was found to be significantly differentially expressed in TAC vs. SHAM hearts, supporting echocardiographic findings [e.g. *nppa* (FC: 4.216, p<0.001), *nppb* (FC: 1.799, p<0.001), *atp2a2* (FC: -0.898, p<0.001), *myh7* (FC: 1.424, p<0.001), and several collagene genes].

Results of the bulk RNA sequencing were further filtered for a total of 288 GPCR genes (*Figure 2/A.*). Of these, 69 GPCR genes were found to be significantly differently expressed in TAC vs. SHAM hearts, 53 of which were up-regulated, and 16 were down-regulated (*Figure 2/B., left panel; Supplementary table S2* shows all significantly differentially expressed GPCR genes measured by bulk RNA sequencing).

Parallel to the bulk RNA sequencing, we investigated the gene expression of a total of 288 GPCR genes by using ddPCR (*Figure 2/A.*). Of these GPCR genes, ddPCR found 27 genes to be significantly differentially expressed in TAC vs. SHAM hearts, 20 of which were up-regulated, and 7 of which were down-regulated (*Figure 2/B., right panel; Supplementary table S3* shows all significantly differentially expressed GPCR genes measured by ddPCR). After the completion of the transcriptomic analyses, we aimed to compare the cardiac GPCR gene expression profiles measured by bulk RNA sequencing and ddPCR.

Figure 2.

Figure 2: Transcriptional characterization of G-protein coupled receptors in TAC vs. SHAM rat hearts by bulk RNA sequencing and droplet digital PCR. (Panel A) represents the workflow for transcriptional characterization of cardiac G-protein coupled receptors (GPCRs), followed by the comparison of results obtained from bulk RNA sequencing and droplet digital PCR (ddPCR), and by the selecting of GPCRs that were found by both methods to be significantly differentially expressed in a significant correlation. (Panel B) volcano plots showing down- and up-regulation of cardiac GPCR expression measured by bulk RNA sequencing (left figure) and by ddPCR (right figure). (Panel C) upper figure represents correlation between bulk RNA sequencing (Y axis) and ddPCR (X axis) values for gene expression, each dot represents one GPCR gene measured in one sample; lower figure represents GPCR genes that were found to be significantly differentially expressed (sDE) in TAC vs. SHAM rat hearts identified by both methods, only eight of which showed significant correlation between the two methods. (Panel D) box plots showing those eight GPCR genes that were found to be sDE in TAC vs. SHAM rat hearts identified by both methods in significant correlation between the two methods. For each GPCR gene, measurements were obtained from $n=5$ individual rat heart from both the SHAM and the TAC groups. For bulk RNA sequencing, *: $p<0.05$ vs. SHAM, Wald test; for ddPCR, *: $p<0.05$ vs. SHAM, Student's unpaired t -test, shown as mean \pm SEM.

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2.3 Comparative analysis of cardiac GPCR gene expression profiles measured by bulk RNA sequencing and ddPCR shows significant correlation

To compare how GPCR gene expression profiles may differ between bulk RNA sequencing and ddPCR, we performed a correlation between the TPM values (obtained from bulk RNA sequencing data) and the copies/ μ L values (obtained from ddPCR data) of all the 288 cardiac GPCR genes investigated from both the TAC and SHAM animals. The overall results of both methods showed significant correlation (Figure 2/C., upper figure, Spearman $R=0.603$, $P<0.001$).

To avoid sources of selection bias for identifying possible GPCR targets in HF, we aimed to focus on GPCR genes that were found to be significantly differentially expressed in TAC vs. SHAM hearts both by bulk RNA sequencing, and by ddPCR, and show a significant correlation between the two methods (Figure 2/A.). 14 cardiac GPCR genes were identified by both methods to be significantly differentially expressed with similar direction of expression changes (up-, or down-regulated) in TAC vs. SHAM hearts, 8 of which genes showed a significant correlation (Figure 2/C., lower figure; Supplementary Figure S1 shows correlation analyses for each sDE GPCRs identified by the two methods). Individual values for gene expression levels of these cardiac GPCR genes are shown on Figure 2/D. (left figure for bulk RNA sequencing, right figure for ddPCR).

2.4 Filtering for novel GPCR targets identifies prostaglandin F 2α receptor to be a potential GPCR target with relevant clinical translatability in heart failure

Of the 8 cardiac GPCR genes that were identified to be significantly differentially expressed in TAC vs. SHAM hearts by both methods and a significant correlation, we sought for genes that (i) can be targeted by commercially available small molecules, and (ii) have not been described yet in the context of HF.

Previous investigations have demonstrated that inhibition of *Npr3* improves HF after myocardial infarction in mice [16], and that *Htr4* was involved in the pathogenesis of ischemic HF in rats [17]. However, to the best of our knowledge, *Ptgfr* was demonstrated to be involved in atherosclerosis and blood pressure regulation [18], [19], bleomycin-induced pulmonary fibrosis [20], as well as in the collagen synthesis of cardiac fibroblasts [21], but *Ptgfr* has never been investigated in the pathogenesis of systolic dysfunction so far.

All in all, *Ptgfr* was chosen to be the candidate for further analyses, as this GPCR gene (i) showed a significant increase in TAC vs. SHAM hearts both by bulk RNA sequencing and ddPCR, with a significant correlation between the two methods (Spearman $R=0.817$, $P=0.011$, Supplementary figure S1), (ii) has a commercially available antagonist (AL-8810), and (iii) has not been described yet in the context of HF.

In addition, given that *Cysltr1* also fits to most of the above stated criteria [as (i) the expression profile of *Cysltr1* also significantly correlates between bulk RNA sequencing and ddPCR, and (ii) *Cysltr1* has already approved antagonists that are currently indicated in maintenance treatment of asthma], however, was previously brought in touch with HF [22], *Cysltr1* was also further characterized, results of which are shown in the Supplementary material.

2.5 *Ptgfr* is expressed by cardiac fibroblasts and cardiomyocytes

First we aimed to characterize which cell types of the cardiac tissue expresses *Ptgfr*. To this end, we performed RNAScope in situ hybridization analyses on the cardiac tissue of mice. We sought for co-localization of *Ptgfr* mRNA with markers of cardiomyocytes (RYR2), endothelial cells (CD31), fibroblast cells (VIM), smooth muscle cells (TAGLN), or macrophages (CD68). We found that *Ptgfr* gene was primarily expressed on RYR2+ cardiomyocytes and VIM+ fibroblast cells (Figure 3/A. and 3/B., respectively, Supplementary figure S2 shows representative RNA Scope images of *Ptgfr* expression in CD31+, TAGLN+

and CD68+ cardiac cells). Our findings showed similar results to that of the Tabula Muris open dataset for single cell transcriptomic data [23].

On the other hand, *Cysltr1* shows an expression profile that is not specific to certain cardiac cells, but is rather globally expressed, as measured by Tabula Muris [23]. Nevertheless, single cell RNAseq of mouse hearts showed that *Cysltr1* is predominantly expressed on macrophages [24] (Supplementary figure S3/A.). Representative RNA Scope images show an expression of *Cysltr1* on RYR2+ cardiomyocytes and VIM+ fibroblast cells as well as in endothelial cell populations (Supplementary figure S3/B-F).

Figure 3.

Figure 3: Prostaglandin F_{2α} receptor expression profile in murine hearts. (A) and (B) demonstrated representative RNA-Scope images of murine hearts showing *Ptgfr* expression on cardiomyocytes (Ryr2⁺ cells) and cardiac fibroblasts (Vim⁺ cells), respectively, with no technical replication or quantification.

2.6 *Ptgfr* inhibition by AL-8810 reverts angiotensin-II induced hypertrophy of neonatal rat cardiomyocytes.

Cardiomyocytes were identified to express *Ptgfr* in murines, as shown above. As the TAC model of HF is characterized by pressure overload induced cardiac hypertrophy, we aimed to test the effect of *Ptgfr*-inhibition in an *in vitro* model that recapitulates these characteristics of TAC model. To this end, we used an *in vitro* model of ANG-II-induced hypertrophy of neonatal rat cardiomyocytes, as described previously [25] (Figure 4/A). In this model, we tested the effect of AL-8810, a highly selective *Ptgfr* inhibitor of lower (1 μ M) or higher (10 μ M) concentrations. These concentrations were selected based on previous publications using AL-8810 on *in vitro* cell cultures [21], [26]–[28].

We found that ANG-II treatment resulted in a significant, ~1.25-fold increase in cell surface area of NRCM cells compared to the vehicle treated group (Figure 4/B. and 4/C.). Cardiomyocyte hypertrophy could be reverted by the 10 μ M, but not the 1 μ M concentrations of AL-8810 treatment (Figure 4/B. and 4/C.). This is the first demonstration of the anti-hypertrophic effect of *Ptgfr*-inhibition on cardiomyocytes.

In the same experimental setup, the effect of montelukast (Monte), a selective *Cysltr1* inhibitor of lower (1 μ M) or higher (10 μ M) concentrations showed no anti-hypertrophic effect (Supplementary figure S4).

Figure 4.

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Figure 4.: Effect of Prostaglandin F_{2α} receptor inhibition on *in vitro* angiotensin-II-induced cardiomyocyte hypertrophy. (A) represents the experimental workflow of neonatal rat cardiomyocyte (NRCM) cell culturing, induction of hypertrophy by angiotensin-II (ANG-II), treatment with prostaglandin F_{2α} receptor (*Ptgfr*) antagonist AL8810 in lower (1μM) and higher (10μM) doses, and measurement of cell surface area (CSA) after phalloidin staining. (B) shows significant increase in CSA of NRCM cells by ANG-II, which could be reverted by 10 μM of AL8810; biological replicates of n=5-9/group, *: p<0.05 vs. ANG-II, One-way ANOVA, Dunett's post hoc test, shown as mean ± SEM. (C) shows representative images of phalloidin staining for each treatment groups.

3. Discussion

Here we demonstrate for the first time that *Ptgfr*, a cardiac GPCR is a potential pharmacological target in HF showing a significantly increased expression in TAC vs. SHAM hearts of rats. *Ptgfr* was identified as a result of a systematic screening for cardiac GPCR genes to be differentially expressed in TAC vs. SHAM rat hearts using bulk deep RNA sequencing, as well as ddPCR, a method that – to the best of our knowledge – was used for the first time for target screening purposes (*Graphical abstract*). In line with the literature, *Ptgfr* was demonstrated to be expressed in cardiac muscle cells and fibroblasts. Finally, here we show that inhibition of *Ptgfr* by AL-8810 prevents *in vitro* cardiomyocyte hypertrophy induced by Ang-II, also supporting that *Ptgfr* is a potential pharmacological target in HF.

To enable identification of drugs that are possible candidates of drug repurposing for a novel indication in HF, we aimed to identify GPCRs that show significantly different expression in TAC vs. SHAM hearts, as GPCRs are the largest family of targets for already approved drugs – agonists, antagonists or partial agonists – currently available on the market. To conduct a systematic screening of cardiac GPCRs with reduced risk of subjective bias, we first assessed the cardiac GPCR gene expression both by bulk RNA sequencing and ddPCR, and filtered only for those candidates that (i) were identified by both methods to be significantly differentially expressed in TAC vs. SHAM rat hearts, and (ii) show significant correlation in levels of gene expression measured by both methods. Only 8 of the total of 288 GPCRs met the above criteria, majority of which have already been tested in previous studies of cardiovascular diseases, a fact that supports the validity of the currently used target screening approach.

Of these GPCRs, we aimed to further characterize *Ptgfr*, as this GPCR (i) shows a significantly increased expression level in failing vs. normal rat and human hearts, as also shown by the single-nucleus transcriptomic data of human failing hearts from patients with dilated or hypertrophic cardiomyopathy [29] (available through the Broad Institute's Single Cell Portal under project ID SCP1303), a finding that supports potential translatability into the clinical settings, (ii) has a high abundance in the cardiac tissue, and especially on cardiac ventricular fibroblast and cardiomyocytes (iii) can be targeted by a highly selective commercially available antagonist, AL-8810, and (iv) is novel to be described in the context of HF and cardiomyocyte hypertrophy. Previous publications also evidence that prostaglandin-F_{2α} (PGF_{2α}) - *Ptgfr* axis may play a pivotal role in cardiovascular diseases [30], [31]. An early study by Rabinowitz and colleagues described that PGF_{2α} is mainly produced by cardiac fibroblasts, which increases by myocardial ischemia [32]. Later, it has been demonstrated that PGF_{2α} further promotes PGF_{2α} formation by a feed-forward fashion, which enhances fibrosis [20], [33], [34].

Beside the role of PGF_{2α} - *Ptgfr* axis in fibrosis, Lai et al. demonstrated that *in vitro* treatment of NRCM with PGF_{2α} results in cardiomyocyte hypertrophy comparable to that of induced by phenylephrine and endothelin-1. This finding was paralleled by a ten-fold increase in the production of atrial natriuretic peptide, and was specific only to PGF_{2α} amongst all investigated prostanoids (i.e. PGA₂, PGB₂, PGD₂, PGF_{2α}, PGI₂, carbaprostacyclin and a thromboxane analogue), as other prostaoids could not cause hypertrophy [35]. Moreover, a seminal study by Yu and colleagues showed that deletion or disruption of *Ptgfr* (i) leads to reduced blood pressure, (ii) lowers activity of the renin-

angiotensin-aldosterone-system, and perhaps most importantly, (iii) attenuates atherogenesis in LDLR^{-/-} mice [18].

Regarding the relationship between PGF2 α - *Ptgfr* axis and HF, Mallat et al. showed that 8-iso-PGF2 α is significantly elevated in pericardial fluid of patients with HF, level of which significantly and positively correlates with HF severity [36]. In the current study we demonstrate that expression of *Ptgfr* shows a significant change in TAC vs. SHAM rat hearts, and that inhibition of this GPCR prevents Ang-II-induced cardiomyocyte hypertrophy *in vitro*. This finding is in alignment with previous publications, emphasizing that inhibition of *Ptgfr* could be beneficial in patients with cardiovascular disease, and more specifically, with HF, as discussed above.

Other GPCRs found by the current screening approach to be potential targets in HF were also touched upon by previous studies. For instance, the expression of *Npr3*, a receptor that is believed to be involved in natriuretic peptide clearance, was found to be significantly elevated in failing rat and human hearts [37], [38]. The inhibition of *Npr3* by osteocrin (either by exogenous administration, or in osteocrin-transgenic mice) results in a significantly increased survival of mice undergoing myocardial infarction induced chronic HF, accompanied by improved cardiac function, lesser degree of cardiac inflammatory processes, and smaller ischemic area [16]. In another set of experiments using isoproterenol-induced *in vivo* model of HF, intramyocardial administration of an *Npr3* siRNA reduced cardiac hypertrophy and fibrosis, and elevated the levels of circulating A-type natriuretic peptide [39]. In addition, microRNAs (more precisely, miR-100 and miR-143) were also identified to be novel candidates for treating HF through interacting with *Npr3* expression [40][41].

Aplnr, a GPCR that shares remarkable homology with the angiotensin-II type 1 receptor, was found to be significantly downregulated in failing vs. normal rat hearts in the current experiments. Activation of *Aplnr* by elabela was shown to revert TAC-induced HF and Ang-II-induced hypertension in mice [42]. In addition, treatment with an *Aplnr* agonist reduced myocardial infarct size, and increased serum nitric oxide level in rats [43]. Of interest, a complete loss of apelin – an endogenous ligand of *Aplnr* – results in increased mortality of mice with myocardial infarction, paralleled by increase in infarct size and inflammation [44].

In the current *in vivo* experiments, we found that level of *Cysltr1* expression is significantly increased in TAC vs. SHAM rat hearts, a finding that is also partially supported by the data derived from single nucleus RNA sequencing of human hearts showing a tendentious – but not significant – elevation in failing vs. normal cardiac tissues [29]. Remarkably, antagonists of *Cysltr1*, i.e. montelukast or zafirlukast are currently available on the market indicated for the maintenance treatment of asthma, a fact showing that antagonists of *Cysltr1* are potential candidates of drug repurposing for a novel indication in HF, which is also supported by other clinical and preclinical studies. For instance, Hoxha and colleagues demonstrated that the use of montelukast in asthmatic patients significantly decreases the incidence of cardiovascular events in a propensity-score matched study, compared to non-users [45]. This is in parallel to the finding of Ingelsson et al., also showing that montelukast may have a potential role for secondary prevention of cardiovascular disease [46]. Moreover, a recent preclinical study demonstrated that montelukast improves cardiac function in a dose-dependent manner in a mouse model of TAC-induced HF [22]. Overall, the screening approach established in the current study was able to identify *Cysltr1* as a highly potential pharmacological target, antagonist of which is a candidate of drug repurposing for HF.

Other cardiac GPCRs with significantly different expression in TAC vs. SHAM rat hearts identified only by ddPCR in the current study were also shown to be involved in the pathogenesis of HF. For instance, the pituitary adenylate cyclase-activating polypeptide (PACAP) receptor type 1 (*Adcyp1r1*) was previously shown to mediate the detrimental effects of PACAP, a neuropeptide in HF of different etiologies [47], [48]. Endothelin and its receptors (*Ednra*, *Ednrb*) were also previously associated with HF, however,

inhibition of endothelin receptors by bosentan failed to improve outcomes of patients with severe chronic HF [49]. Antagonism of glucagon receptor (*Gcgr*), a GPCR showing significantly lower expression in TAC vs. SHAM rat hearts, was previously demonstrated to improve cardiac function of animals with HF of ischemic and non-ischemic etiologies [50]. A detailed *in silico* analysis on failing and healthy human hearts has demonstrated that cardiac GPCRs encoded by the *F2rl2* and *Sstr5* genes could serve as novel and potential biomarkers or therapeutic targets of HF [51], similarly to our findings identified by ddPCR. Since, to the best of our knowledge, the remaining cardiac GPCRs identified by the current screening approach using ddPCR (*Supplementary table S3.*) were not yet brought in context with the pathophysiology of HF, future studies investigating the role of these GPCRs in HF would be of great interest.

Despite promising results, there are several limitations to the currently used screening approach. We assessed the level of GPCR gene expression, because GPCRs are difficult and often unsuccessful to be detected at a protein level (either by western blot, immunohistochemistry, or by proteomics). This approach may be confounded by the lack of information regarding post-translational processes of GPCRs, however, transcriptomic measurements of GPCR expression are widely used and in the present work allowed for systematic screening of a total of 288 GPCRs. Another important characteristic of the current screening approach could be that GPCRs showing lower absolute expression levels may not be measured by ddPCR with high reliability. This is demonstrated by the pattern of the correlation analysis between the gold standard bulk RNA sequencing and ddPCR showing that GPCR genes with lower expression levels (i.e. TPM and copies/uL<1) could be more differentiated by bulk RNA sequencing than that by ddPCR. On the other hand, however, GPCR genes with higher expression levels (i.e. TPM and copies/uL>1) could be differentiated with both methods similarly, and overall, the correlation was significant and meaningful between the two methods. Finally, although promising, these results regarding *Ptgfr*, and *Ptgfr*-inhibition should be validated in a variety of *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies. For instance, on-target and off-target effects of AL-8810, and other *ptgfr*-antagonists (as well as agonists) in similar cell culture studies deserve further investigations in the future. Furthermore, beside the TAC model of HF, *Ptgfr*-modulation should be tested in models of myocardial infarction-induced-HF, Ang-II or isoprenaline-induced cardiac damage, or aorto-ventricular-fistula-induced HF in different species. Moreover, where possible, the influence of sex and age should also be taken into account in future *in vivo* studies.

4. Materials and Methods

4.1 Ethical approval

This investigation complies with the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals published by the US National Institutes of Health (NIH Publication No. 85-23, revised 1996), and with the guidelines from Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes. Investigations were compliant with local directives and approved by The Animal Ethics Committees at Semmelweis University, Budapest (PE/EA/1784-7/2017, and PEI/001/2374-4/2015). This study was conducted in accordance with the ARRIVE guidelines.

4.2 Rat model of transverse aortic constriction induced cardiac dysfunction and hypertrophy

Animals were housed under standard conditions (25±2°C and constant 12 h light/dark) and allowed free access to a standard rodent chow diet and tap water ad libitum. Prior to the interventions, at least 7 days of acclimatization period was applied. For all *in vivo* studies, animals were randomly assigned to experimental groups, and data analyses were performed by 1-3 independent persons in a blinded fashion. Animals were excluded from further analyses if iatrogenic death or severe complications occurred dur-

ing or after surgery (e.g. excessive bleeding, acute HF). During the surgery, body temperature was continuously monitored and maintained at 37°C. Pain reflex was monitored by pinching the toes every 5-10 minutes.

Male Wistar rats (2–3 weeks old, 50–75 g, purchased from Toxi-Coop Zrt., Dunakeszi, Hungary) were randomly assigned to sham (SHAM) or transverse aortic constriction (TAC) surgery. Under isoflurane anesthesia (5 V/V% isoflurane for induction and 1.5-2 V/V% isoflurane for maintenance after orotracheal intubation, 100% O₂), after removal of the chest hair and disinfecting the surgical area, a left anterolateral thoracotomy was performed in the 2nd intercostal space under surgical stereomicroscope. After the partial removal of the thymus, the aortic arch between the brachiocephalic trunk and the left common carotid artery was identified by atraumatically dissecting the surrounding connective tissue. The aorta was constricted to the external size of a 21-gauge needle in the TAC animals. SHAM animals underwent the same procedure without the completion of the aortic constriction. Thereafter, thorax was closed by suturing the 2nd and 3rd ribs followed by the suturing of the skin. To prevent postoperative pain and dehydration, tramadol and physiological saline (10 mg/kg in 0.5 mL) was injected subcutaneously before the animals regained consciousness. After a median follow-up of 15 weeks, echocardiography was performed and animals were euthanized by terminal arterial blood collection under deep anaesthesia, followed by cardiac sample collection for further analyses.

4.3 Echocardiography

An echocardiographic imaging unit (Vivid i; GE Healthcare, Waukesha, WI) with a 13-MHz linear probe (GE 12L-RS; GE Healthcare) at a constant frame rate of 218 frames/sec was used for echocardiographic measurements. Animals were anaesthetized by isoflurane (5 V/V% isoflurane for induction and 1.5-2 V/V% isoflurane for maintenance through a nose cone, 100% O₂) and were placed onto a heating pad in a supine position to maintain body temperature at 37°C. Chest hair was removed to obtain an optimal acoustic window. Echocardiographic cines were taken in 2D parasternal long-axis (PLAX) and short-axis (PSAX) views. Left ventricular end-systolic and end-diastolic volumes were derived from the rotational volumes of the left ventricular trace at diastole and systole, around the long axis line of the spline (LVESV, LVEDV respectively), obtained from the PLAX view in B-mode acquisition. Left ventricular stroke volume (LVSV) was calculated as LVEDV-LVESV. Left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) was calculated as $[LVSV/LVEDV]*100$. Left ventricular cardiac output (LVCO) was calculated as $[\text{heart rate} * LVSV] / 1000$. Left ventricular end-systolic and end-diastolic diameters (LVESD and LVEDD, respectively), as well as left ventricular anterior and posterior wall thicknesses in diastole (LVAWTd and LVPWTd, respectively) were obtained from the PSAX view in M-mode acquisition at midpapillary level. Relative wall thickness (RWT) was calculated as $2 * LVPWTd / LVEDD$. LVMass was calculated according to the modified cubic formula as $1.04 * [(LVEDD + LVAWd + LVPWd) * 3 - LVIDd * 3] * 0.8 + 0.6$. Cines were obtained and analysed (EchoPAC; GE Healthcare) in a blinded fashion by a single operator.

4.4 RNA isolation

Total RNA was isolated from rat hearts by using a chloroform/isopropanol precipitation method. Briefly, Qiazol® (Qiagen, The Netherlands) was added to each sample and homogenized with TissueLyser (Qiagen, The Netherlands). Homogenates were then centrifuged, and from the clean upper phase, DNA and protein were precipitated with chloroform, followed by precipitation of the total RNA using isopropanol. Pellets were washed four times with 75% ethanol (vWR, PA, USA), then total RNA was resuspended in nuclease-free water. Finally, RNA concentrations for each sample were determined by spectrophotometry (Implen Nanophotometer® N60, München, Germany).

4.5 RNA sequencing and bioinformatic analysis

The RNA Integrity Numbers and RNA concentration were determined by RNA ScreenTape system with 2200 TapeStation (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA)

and RNA HS Assay Kit with Qubit 3.0 Fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA).

For mRNA-Seq library construction, NEXTFLEX® Rapid Directional RNA-Seq Kit 2.0 with Poly(A) Beads 2.0 (PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA, USA) was applied according to the manufacturer's protocol. The quality and quantity of the library was determined by using High Sensitivity DNA1000 ScreenTape system with 2200 TapeStation (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) and dsDNA HS Assay Kit with Qubit 3.0 Fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Pooled libraries were diluted to 1.6 pM for 2x80 bp paired-end sequencing with 150-cycle High Output v2 Kit on the NextSeq 500 Sequencing System (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA) according to the manufacturer's protocol.

During preprocessing of raw sequencing data by Cutadapt (version 3.0) adapter sequences, poly(A) tails and bases with a Phred score below 30 were trimmed, reads below a length of 19 nt were filtered out [52], [53]. Quality of reads was checked by FastQC (version 0.11.8) and MultiQC (version 1.7) softwares [54]. Alignment and annotation of reads were performed by Hisat2 (version 2.0.4) and featureCounts (version 2.0.0), respectively using Ensembl Rnor 6.0. reference genome and annotation [55], [56]. Sequence alignment map (SAM) files were converted to binary form by Samtools (version 1.9) [56], [57]. Differential expression analysis and calculation of transcripts per million (TPM) was conducted in R environment (version 3.2.3) with the usage of DESeq2 (version 1.10.1) package [58]. P values of Wald tests were adjusted by Benjamini-Hochberg method due to multiple comparisons [59]. After the completion of whole transcriptome sequencing and bioinformatic analysis, data was screened for GPCRs.

4.6 Droplet digital PCR

Screening and quantitative assessment of cardiac GPCR expression were performed by droplet digital polymerase chain reaction (QX200 Droplet Digital PCR System; Bio-Rad Laboratories, CA, USA) using a pre-designed assay kit allowing for the measurement of 288 GPCRs (PrimePCR Pathway Plate, 96 well; GPCR Tier 1-2-3 R96, Rat; Bio-Rad Laboratories, CA, USA). Absolute quantification of the target molecules was performed using water-oil emulsion droplet technology. Briefly, each sample was fractionated into 15-20,000 droplets by QX200 Droplet Generator (DG32 Automated Droplet Generator Cartridges, Automated Droplet Generation Oil for EvaGreen; Bio-Rad Laboratories, CA, USA), and PCR amplification of the template molecules occurs in each individual droplet. Detection of gene expression measured by QX Droplet Reader System using ddPCR Droplet Reader Oil (Bio-Rad Laboratories, CA, USA). cDNA was synthesized from 4 µg total RNA by iScript Advanced cDNA Synthesis Kit (Bio-Rad Laboratories, CA, USA) according to the manufacturer's protocol. cDNA was further diluted 20× with RNase free water. All reactions were carried out using QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix (Bio-Rad Laboratories, CA, USA) and 100 ng of input cDNA. Level of GPCR gene expression, i.e. copies/µL was quantified by QuantaSoft™ Analysis Pro (version 1.0.596, Bio-Rad Laboratories, CA, USA).

4.7 Neonatal rat cardiomyocyte model of hypertrophy

In vitro model of cardiomyocyte hypertrophy was performed as described earlier [25][60]. Briefly, primary neonatal rat cardiomyocytes (NRCM) were isolated from neonatal rats of both sexes (post-partum days 1-2). After disinfection by 70% ethanol, animals were euthanized by cervical dislocation, followed by the excision of the hearts, which were then transferred into phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH=7.2). Then, ventricles were separated and gently minced by using fine forceps, followed by a digestion in 0.25% trypsin solution (5 mL per heart) at 37°C for 90 min. Cell suspension was then centrifuged at 300g at 4°C for 15 min, supernatant was discarded, and pellets were resuspended in growth medium (glucose and glutamine-rich Dulbecco's MEM [10-014-CV, Corning Inc, Corning, NY, USA] supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum, 1% L-glutamine

[25030081, Life Technologies Corporation, CA, USA] and 1% antibiotic/antimycotic solution [30004CI, Corning Inc, NY, USA]) and plated onto 6-well plates ($1.0\text{--}1.2 \times 10^6$ cells/well, in 2 mL growth medium) to eliminate fibroblasts at 37°C for 25 min (pre-plating step). Cells of the supernatant were then re-plated onto fresh 24-well plates onto coverslips ($1.0\text{--}1.2 \times 10^5$ cells/well, in 1 mL growth medium), and were kept in 5% CO₂ incubator at 37°C. On the following day, medium was changed to a fresh medium.

To achieve hypertrophy of NRCM cells, medium was changed again to a fresh medium at the second day after the isolation, and cells were treated with 1 µM of angiotensin-II (ANG-II; A9525, Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA) in DMSO, as vehicle. For control treatment, cells received DMSO only. ANG-II treated cells received either no additional treatment, or AL-8810 (a selective inhibitor for *Ptgfr*; A3846, Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA) or montelukast (Monte; a selective inhibitor of *Cysltr1*; GX0261, Glentham Life Sciences Ltd., Cersham, UK) in DMSO at the concentrations of 1 µM or 10 µM. The volume of the vehicle was equal in all the groups. 24 hours after start of treatment, cells were fixed with 2% paraformaldehyde in 1×PBS for 5 min at room temperature, then permeabilized with 0.2% Triton-X (Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA) for 10 min. Slides were then stained with phalloidin iFluor-594 (ab176757, Abcam, Cambridge, UK) and DAPI, and images were taken by Leica LMD6 microscope. The surface area of at least 150 cells from 6 independent and random fields was measured by two blinded and independent experimenters using the ImageJ software. The average cell surface area of all measured cells in a treatment group was used as one data point, and each datapoint represents one biological replicate. We pre-defined the following exclusion criteria: (i) if the ANG-II treatment increased the cell surface area by <5%, and (ii) if cell viability was <90%.

4.8 RNA Scope® In Situ Hybridization Assay

The in situ hybridization assay was performed on the cross section slides of the ventricles harvested from mouse heart samples using RNA Scope® Multiplex Fluorescent Kit v2 according to the manufacturer's instructions (Advanced Cell Diagnostics Pharma Assay Services, Newark, CA, United States). Briefly, formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded tissue sections were baked for 1 h at 60°C, and then deparaffinized. Endogenous HRP activity was blocked with hydrogen peroxide (catalog number: 322335) treatment for 10 min at room temperature. Target retrieval was performed for 15 min at 100 °C, followed by Protease Plus (catalog number: 322331) treatment for 15 min at 40 °C. Probes were then hybridized for 2 h at 40 °C (3-plex Positive Control Probe-Mm (catalog number: 320881), 3-plex Negative Control Probe (catalog number: 320871), Mm-*Ptgfr*-O1 (catalog number: 501841, accession no.: NM_008966.3), Mm-*Cysltr1*-C3 (catalog number: 487541-C3, accession no.: NM_021476.5), Mm-*Vim*-C2 (catalog number: 457961-C2, accession no.: NM_011701.4), Mm-*Cd68* (catalog number: 316611, accession no.: NM_009853.1), Mm-*Cd68*-C3 (catalog number: 316611-C3, accession no.: NM_009853.1), Mm-*Pecam1*-C2 (catalog number: 316721-C2, accession no.: NM_001032378.1), Mm-*Ryr2*-C2 (catalog number: 479981-C2, accession no.: NM_023868.2), and Mm-*Tagln*-C2 (catalog number: 480331-C2, accession no.: NM_011526.5)). Cell type-specific markers were used to identify cardiomyocytes with a probe recognizing the mRNA of Ryanodine receptor 2 (RYR2) [61], endothelial cells with a probe recognizing the mRNA of platelet endothelial cell adhesion molecule 1 (PECAM-1, a.k.a CD31) [62], fibroblast cells with a probe recognizing the mRNA of Vimentin (VIM) [63], [64], smooth muscle cells with a probe recognizing the mRNA of transgelin (TAGLN) [65], and macrophages with a probe recognizing the mRNA of cluster of differentiation 68 (CD68) [66], respectively. Afterwards RNA Scope amplification was performed followed by signal development with TSA fluorophores (TSA-Cy3, TSA-FITC, Akoya Biosciences, Marlborough, MA, United States). Nuclei were counterstained with DAPI (catalog number: 323108) and mounted with Prolong Gold Antifade Reagent (catalog number: 9071S, Cell Signaling Technology, Danvers, MA, United States). Specific RNA staining signal was identified as red/green dots. Fluorescent signals were detected by a Leica DMI8 Confocal microscope (Leica, Wetzlar, Germany).

4.9 Statistical analysis

All data were generated from at least four independent experiments. All values are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism (version 8.0.1). $P < 0.05$ was considered significant. Normal distribution of data was tested by Shapiro-Wilk normality test. For comparisons between two groups, either parametric two-tailed Student's t-test, or nonparametric Mann-Whitney U-test was performed. For comparison of multiple groups to one control group, one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc test was used. The post hoc tests were conducted only if F in ANOVA test achieved $P < 0.05$ and there was no significant variance in homogeneity. For correlation analysis of two continuous variables, Spearman's rho (R) was computed. ROUT analysis was performed to identify outliers, with Q value = 1%.

5. Conclusions

Here we established a systematic screening approach by using ddPCR in comparison to bulk RNA sequencing data, and found that cardiac GPCR expression differs in hearts with pressure-overload-induced cardiac dysfunction vs. healthy hearts in a rat model. In addition, we demonstrated that some of these GPCRs are targets for already approved drugs that are available commercially. Here we show for the first time that *Ptgfr* expression is significantly increased in TAC vs. SHAM rat hearts, a GPCR that is primarily expressed by cardiac fibroblast and cardiomyocytes, and that inhibition of *Ptgfr* by the small molecule AL 8810 prevents Ang-II-induced cardiomyocyte hypertrophy *in vitro*. In addition, the current screening approach was also able to identify other cardiac GPCRs that already have been investigated in the context of HF, and that antagonists of *Cysltr1*, i.e., montelukast or zafirlukast could be potential candidates of drug repurposing for a novel indication in HF, which deserves further investigation.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: www.mdpi.com/xxx/s1, Figure S1: title; Table S1: title; Video S1: title.

Author Contributions: NVS and VÉT participated in designing the study and conducting the *in vitro* experiments, analysed data and wrote the manuscript. RN, ZO participated in the *in vitro* experiments. IV performed the RNA Scope representative images on samples obtained from TGG. NN and CB participated in droplet digital PCR experiments. BV and BÁ performed bioinformatic analyses on RNA sequencing data. MR and TR performed the *in vivo* experiments. FB provided single cell RNA sequencing data. LCZ, PP, AG and PF revised the manuscript and intellectual content, and provided professional advice. ZVV designed the experiments, wrote and revised the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Institutional Review Board Statement: This investigation complies with the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals published by the US National Institutes of Health (NIH Publication No. 85–23, revised 1996), and with the guidelines from Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes. Investigations were compliant with local directives and approved by The Animal Ethics Committees at Semmelweis University, Budapest (PE/EA/1784-7/2017, and PEI/001/2374-4/2015). This study was conducted in accordance with the ARRIVE guidelines.

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Data Availability Statement: The datasets used and/or analysed are available from the corresponding author upon request. RNA sequencing datasets will be deposited in the ArrayExpress database.

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Conflicts of Interest: PF is the founder and CEO, and AG and BÁ are involved in the management of Pharmahungary Group, a group of R&D services. Other authors declare no conflict of interest.

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